

MEDICAL SCIENCES

COMPLICATIONS OF TREATMENT OF DEFECTS OF HARD DENTAL TISSUES

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ABSTRACT

Despite advances in the use of restorative materials and the constant improvement of direct and indirect restoration techniques, the number of unsatisfactory results is still significant. Since dentists make mistakes at different stages of treatment when performing restorations, the problem of improving methods for restoring hard dental tissues occupies one of the leading places among the pressing problems of modern dentistry.

Keywords: defects of hard dental tissues, restoration, complications.

Conclusion. Our research allows us to state that errors at the stage of choosing a method for treating defects in hard dental tissues lead to clinical situations with an unfavorable prognosis for such teeth, including their loss.

Relevance Despite the rapid development of dentistry, the introduction of the latest techniques and technologies into practice, defects of hard dental tissues remain the most common form of damage to the dental system [1]. Defects in the hard tissues of the tooth crown are most often formed as a result of caries. It is worth noting that in modern clinical practice, dentists have been offered methods of direct, indirect and semi-direct restoration to replace defects in the hard tissues of the tooth [4–6]. Complications after restoration are often caused by mistakes made by dentists at the stage of choosing a treatment method [7, 8].

Based on the achievements of dental science in the field of improving the adhesion of restoration materials to dental tissues, there has been a combination of indications for direct and indirect dental restoration [9]. As a result, the indirect method of treatment is rarely used (only 1.5% of all teeth that needed were restored with inlays) and the number of complications increases [10]. Despite advances in the use of restorative materials and the constant improvement of direct and indirect restoration techniques, the number of unsatisfactory ones remains. Since dentists make mistakes at different stages of treatment when performing restorations, the problem of improving methods of restoration of hard dental tissues occupies one of the leading places among the pressing problems of modern dentistry.

Purpose of the study: to study and analyze complications that arise in patients after dental treatment of defects in hard dental tissues. 60 examined. The groups of patients were distributed as follows: the first group consisted of 30 patients in whom, according to traditional indications [11] and treatment protocols, direct restoration was indicated; the second group consisted

of 30 patients in whom, according to traditional indications [11] and treatment protocols, indirect restoration was indicated. Criteria for inclusion of patients in the study: patient without significant somatic diseases; without periodontal tissue diseases; patients with a physiological type of occlusion; patients without dental defects; patients with complaints about previously manufactured restorations; period after previous treatment – from 6 months to 3 years. In all patients, the cause of cavities was a carious process. Thus, the patients of the study groups did not have any additional influences on the state of the dental system and complicating factors that would have influenced the results of the study. Clinical examinations of patients were carried out using classical methods. When examining patients, attention was first paid to complaints associated with previously manufactured restorations. A survey was conducted on the manufacture and period of use of the restoration. We examined the restoration itself using a modified USPHS (United States Public Health Service) method (Ryge G.) [12], paying attention to the material from which it was made and the manufacturing method. It was necessary to take into account the volume of the defect, the remainder of hard tissue-pore teeth after preparation, the condition of the antagonist teeth, and the bite. IROPZ was determined according to V.Yu. Milikevich-tha. Occlusal contacts were determined using occlusal paper. In order to obtain additional data on the depth of destruction, X-ray examinations and diagnosis of secondary caries were carried out using the DIAGNOdent device. We assessed and divided the cracks and fractures of teeth according to the AAE (American Association of Endodontists) classification [13]. The results obtained during the study were subjected to statistical processing using the variation statistics method using the statistical software package Microsoft Excel-2015 and Statistica-8.0. The reliability of all obtained results was determined at the level of $p \leq 0.05$. Results of the study Patients of study groups I and II contacted us with complaints about previously

manufactured restorations. Clinical evaluation of restorations was carried out according to the USPHS method. Moreover, all study groups had patients for whom these restorations needed replacement (with a Charlie score (C)). (32.5±5.2)% – complications were observed before the 1-year period of use of the restoration, (22.5±4.7)% – complications were observed before the 2-year period of use of the restoration, (23.8±4.8) % (13) and complications were observed – complications. 1). All patients of group I had previously had direct restorations made. The results of the clinical assessment of complications that arose after treatment of patients in the first group of subjects were as follows and are presented in Fig. 2. Anatomical shape discrepancy (AF) was noted in 4 cases (15.0±5.6%): there is a significant loss of restorative material with exposure of dentin or spacer material, which is an indication for replacement of the restoration. Disorders of marginal adaptation (MA) were observed in the study of 9 restorations (27.5 ± 7.1%): the instrument is easily inserted into a crack through which exposed dentin and spacer material are visible, or the restoration is mobile or missing, which is an indication for its replacement. Evaluation of restorations in the first group according to the surface roughness (SR) criterion showed that in 6 (20.0 ± 6.3) % of cases the surface of the restoration was deeply porous. It has unequal depressions that are not related to anatomical formations, the surface cannot be corrected by finishing, the surface is broken or there is delamination, which is an indication for its replacement. Presence of marginal discoloration (MD) – in 11 restorations (22.5±6.6)% the discoloration extends towards the pulp, indicating pulp replacement. Having assessed the color consistency (CM) of the restorations, it was noted that the discrepancy between color and transparency was beyond acceptable limits in 6 cases (15.0±5.6)%. The latter needed replacement. that in 14 (35.0 ± 7.5)% of cases there were signs of secondary caries. The second group consisted of 40 patients in whom, according to traditional indications and treatment protocols, indirect restoration was indicated. 3 patients 10% of group II had previously had indirect restorations made, and 27 90% had previously had direct restorations made. In this group, we divided the observed complications into two subgroups: complications in the manufacture of indirect restorations and complications in the manufacture of direct restorations. The subgroup of patients who had complications during the manufacture of indirect restorations consisted of 3 patients: 1 of them complained of a violation of fixation (de-cementation) of the restoration, and another 2 patients complained of a chip of a particle of the indirect restoration. Of course, the too small sample of patients was unrepresentative and did not provide us with objective information about complications during treatment with indirect restorations. The subgroup of patients who had complications during the manufacture of direct restorations consisted of 27 patients. Of these, in 8 cases a significant loss of restoration material was observed (restoration defect), which is an indication for replacement of the restoration. And in 5 cases, a violation of the anatomical shape

of the teeth was revealed when modeling a direct restoration: flattening or absence of hills, bevel of cutting edges, absence of occlusal contacts on the restoration (in this way, doctors “prevented” complications). fillings) restorations, and, according to anamnesis, it is known about repeated losses of these restorations. In patients of the second group, we observed cracks and fractures of teeth. According to the AAE (American Association of Endodontists) classification, we observed 4 cases of “Fractured Cusp” fracture, where there is a complete or partial fracture of the cusp, starting at the crown, moving towards its neck or ending at the gum line. The prognosis for such teeth is favorable and subsequent treatment tactics depended on the depth of the destruction.). The prognosis for such teeth is questionable and depends on the depth of the crack at the root. The prognosis for such teeth was unfavorable, and such teeth were subject to extraction.

Analysis and discussion of the results. Thus, we can summarize that the results of the study of patients in the first group illuminate us with a number of complications, most of which arose as a result of errors made by doctors at various stages of treatment: incorrect choice of color, poor isolation of the cavity from oral fluid, as well as insufficient response . needed replacement. We can say that the treatment of hard tissue defects using the direct restoration method is complex and has its own characteristics. Many unsatisfactory results and complications occur due to doctors’ mistakes made at different stages of treatment. At the same time, the prognosis for such teeth is favorable; these complications do not lead to tooth loss or other factors complicating further dental treatment. An analysis of the previously performed treatment of patients of the second group, in whom, according to traditional indications and treatment protocols, indirect restoration was indicated, reveals a huge problem. After all, only in 5% of cases we observed the correct choice of treatment - indirect restoration. Having analyzed the results of the study of complications in the second group, we noted that in 39.5% of patients there was a discrepancy in the anatomical shape of the tooth due to defects in the filling or incorrect modeling of the restoration. In 39.5% of cases there was a lack of restoration (loss of fillings).

Conclusion

Thus, the research carried out allows us to state that errors at the stage of choosing a method for treating defects in the hard tissues of teeth lead to clinical situations with an unfavorable prognosis for such teeth, including their loss. As a result of the analysis, it was found that only in 5% of cases the correct choice of treatment was observed for patients with defects of hard dental tissues for whom the production of indirect restoration was indicated. restoration modeling. In (39.5±7.9)% of cases there was no restoration, in (5.3±3.6)% of cases there was a fracture of the “Cracked Tooth” tooth, and in (5.3±3.6)% it was complete fracture of the “Split Tooth” tooth, which led to its loss. ical situations with an unfavorable prognosis for such teeth, including their loss. Thus, the conducted studies allow us to state that errors at the stage of choosing a method for treating defects in hard dental tissues

lead to clinical situations with an unfavorable prognosis for such teeth, up to their loss.

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